

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING INTERNET RESOURCES IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract

The article focuses on the importance and benefits of using internet resources to practice and revise newly acquired vocabulary. The goal of this article is to motivate language learners to use digital tools, media, and the Internet to implement these research-based recommendations in innovative ways, i.e., to use technology to enhance learning potential.

Key words: internet resources, internet-based programmes, e-resources, internet literacy, data, websites, access.

Introduction

The use of internet materials for language learning is the most creative area in the practice of English language teaching and learning. Teachers frequently find it difficult to keep students engaged and motivated in classroom practices subjects or activities. One of the advantages of using internet materials is that it provides fresh options for assisting teachers in dealing with this challenge. In recent years, the majority of educators who use internet sources has increased substantially. Whereas the possibilities of online materials for academic use has yet to be thoroughly investigated, and most academic institutions still use computers and internet resources to a minor extent, it is completely obvious that we have started the new information age in which the relationships between technology and the English language are becoming increasingly important.

Nowadays teachers experience several challenges in the classroom since it

is difficult to keep adequate effective classroom management and teachers must provide more students with varied skills. Thus, this article will try to cover the advantages and disadvantages of using online sources in order to provide future studies with necessary data on this sphere.

Some of the advantages of using the internet to learn a language are listed below.

1. Internet resources provide students with a multitude of actual educational materials. It gives students worldwide access to a huge selection of materials from a variety of sources.

2. Learners who use internet sources have more control over the learning process and are less dependent on a teacher, which can contribute to autonomy.

3. Using internet resources allows students to use e - resources other than grammar check, dictionary, and thesaurus..

4. Using internet resources, online teaching is possible. The Internet can be an important platform for delivering online courses.

5. Accessing the Internet takes a fraction of the time it takes to seek through literature. It shows text word by word, phrase by phrase, line by line, question by question, page by page, and so on.

6. Having access to material through internet materials at any time permits the teachers to digest knowledge in a systematic way.

7. The internet allows students to access answers quickly and easily, as well as assess their progress. As a result, it could provide students with immediate feedback

8. Another benefit of using internet sources to learn a language is that computers and electronic gadgets can be used as the primary teacher. Computers do not get exhausted and can perform the same task repeatedly without complaints.

9. Students can utilize internet-based programs to time their work, limit

how much time they have to read a piece or finish a set of exercises, and so on.

10. Students learn independently and at the appropriate ability level content that is relevant to their personal goals and needs, as well as what they are interested in.

11. Teachers and learners can work from anywhere and at any time by using internet, rather than being restricted to a specific time and location in the classroom.

12. The Internet store detailed records of information. Teachers can keep track of individual and group scores and times

13. Internet resources help students reach their full potential by allowing them to work together as a team to accomplish homework more quickly.

14. The internet enable teachers to quickly collect students' electronic projects for analysis purposes and assessment, as well as send and receive homework and notices electronically and follow the progress of a student or group. The internet allows the teacher to send and receive information from all of his or her students in real time..

15. Internet-based programs are capable of performing speedy and precise statistics. They let teachers calculate final score, averages, and standard deviations, as well as analyze individual student and class results numerically.

16. The internet provides a supportive environment for hesitant students to demonstrate themselves and ask any questions.

Disadvantages of Using Internet Resources

In addition to the various advantages, there are also disadvantages to using internet resources. The use of internet resources is not always effective since it has a number of constraints that make it unsuitable for academic purposes. The difficulties to using internet resources can be classified into the following main categories.

1. Internet literacy is essential for both teachers and students therefore

using internet sources needs computer skills in order for a consumer to issue commands and receive results.

2. Despite the presence of a comprehensive manual, certain websites can be hard to navigate. Students must acquire knowledge to correctly use computers and the internet, no matter how simple they are.

3. Internet resources have memory, speed, data flow methodologies, and other limitations. The internet's language teaching resources are still in their infancy.

4. Data processing requires time.

5. Fully understanding how to type is vital for efficient internet use as most data are entered by typing. There are a few voice search resources available online nowadays , but they aren't very common owing to lack of growth.

6. In general, all websites do exactly what they are supposed to do. All internet resources have their own disadvantages and limitations. After finishing a quiz, some linguistic resources, for example, display the final result without offering any extra information about the mistakes.

7. Some online materials may not be able to perform to the user's specific needs.

8. Accessing online sources will not be able to meet unexpected user requests and demands because systems can only perform what they were designed to do.

9. The price of computers and internet access is prohibitively expensive. In addition, there is a substantial number of supplementary technology. A large amount of additional technology is also required. Internet connection on the computer is frequently out of reach for low-income students and educational institutions.

10. A specific classroom is necessary, as well as employees to keep the equipment and network functioning efficiently.

11. Internet resources must be evaluated critically because the majority of them were not created with English learners in mind. Native speakers frequently utilize colloquial terms that are inappropriate for classroom use.

12. Teachers must also be educated in order to better explain topics and utilize information technologies.

Conclusion

This article looked at the benefits and drawbacks of using the Internet to learn a language. We can only improve the environment for Internet-based language learning by designing appropriate hardware and software. Internet-based language learning will undoubtedly have a bright future because we live in an information age.

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